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Design of an SiC Inverter for a Residential Heat-Pump

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Abstract—The design of a SiC-based frequency inverter for a residential heating heat pump is presented. The nominal power of the hermetically sealed heat pump scroll compressor is 3 kW. With a margin for future power increase, the frequency inverter was designed for a nominal power of 5 kW, with DC link voltage of 650 V. The paper describes the design and experimental validation of the device, made in two versions. One version was with surface mount SiC MOSFETs and the second with through-hole components. Experimental results up to 2.5 kW are shown. The designed inverter was tested with an induction motor on a dynamometer. Thermal measurement was also performed, and this resulting in a presented issues with gate driver DC/DC converters.

Index Terms—SiC inverter, heat pump, inverter design.

I. INTRODUCTION

The frequency inverter described in this paper is designed for a residential heat pump. One of the goals is to increase the inverter efficiency and hence the efficiency of the heat pump.

The frequency inverter drives a hermetically sealed scroll compressor with a permanent magnet synchronous motor (PMSM). In the current application, the PMSM power is max. 3 kW at 6000 min^{-1} , however the inverter is designed for a maximal power of 5 kW as the design should be reused in future applications.

Improving the energy efficiency of residential heating systems is an increasingly important task due to rising energy costs and increasing emphasis on sustainability. One of the most promising approaches to achieving high energy efficiency is the integration of wide bandgap (WBG) semiconductors into power conversion systems such as frequency inverters for heat pumps. Silicon carbide (SiC) devices, in particular, offer considerable advantages in switching performance, thermal resistance, and efficiency compared to traditional silicon-based power devices [1].

Residential heat pumps are gaining increasing attention for energy-efficient climate control, where inverter-driven compressors enable variable-speed operation and improved coefficient of performance (COP). The choice of semiconductor technology in the inverter significantly affects the efficiency of

the system, its thermal performance, and its long-term reliability. WBG semiconductors are attractive for these applications as a result of their superior material properties compared to conventional silicon. SiC MOSFETs offer higher breakdown voltage, lower on-resistance, and faster switching, enabling inverters with reduced switching losses and compact designs [2].

For residential heat pump applications, where efficiency under partial load is critical, the adoption of SiC can result in substantial improvements. Studies show that SiC-based inverters allow higher switching frequencies and smaller passive components, without significantly compromising efficiency [3]. This makes them well suited for low- to mid-power applications such as household HVAC systems, especially where quiet operation and compactness are valued [4].

Wide-bandgap semiconductors have attracted significant attention in recent years due to their superior material properties—including higher breakdown voltage, thermal conductivity, and switching speed—compared to conventional silicon devices. These advantages make SiC-based inverters highly attractive for residential heat pump applications, where efficiency, compactness, and thermal reliability are paramount.

Several studies have quantified the benefits of SiC over silicon IGBTs or MOSFETs. Mathe and Raju [5] conducted simulations of a three-phase SPWM inverter and found that switching losses in a SiC MOSFET design are up to 42 % lower than those of a silicon IGBT inverter at a switching frequency of 15 kHz [5]. Liu et al. [6] performed an experimental comparison in an LCL-filtered three-phase grid-connected inverter, demonstrating that SiC MOSFETs support higher switching frequencies enabling higher power density and lower harmonic distortion relative to Si IGBT designs.

A crucial aspect of inverter design is the choice between discrete power devices and integrated power modules. Discrete SiC MOSFETs, commonly packaged in TO-247 or similar formats, provide cost advantages and layout flexibility. However, they suffer from higher parasitic inductance and less efficient thermal paths due to single-sided cooling [7]. Power modules, on the contrary, offer lower loop inductance, better thermal performance through ceramic substrates and baseplates, and often include integrated current or temperature sensing. Although more expensive, they simplify assembly and

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can be more reliable under thermal cycling.

Thermal management is a key challenge in both discrete and modular designs. Although SiC devices are rated for high junction temperatures, effective heat extraction is necessary to avoid hotspots and ensure long-term reliability. This is especially relevant when surface-mounted devices are used, as PCB-based thermal dissipation is often limited. Recent work by Yao et al. shows that adopting a press-pack-inspired double-sided cooling solution for discrete SiC MOSFETs can reduce thermal resistance by nearly 50% and significantly improve inverter performance [8].

Another consideration is the efficiency of the auxiliary circuits, such as the gate driver power supplies. Low-efficiency isolated DC/DC converters used to drive high-side and low-side switches may generate excessive localized heating, becoming the dominant thermal issue in some designs [9]. High-efficiency gate-driver ICs and integrated drivers with improved thermal profiles are therefore critical, particularly in space-constrained inverter layouts.

This paper presents the design and experimental validation of a 5 kW SiC-based inverter intended for use in a residential heat pump. Two design iterations are discussed, focusing on thermal management, component selection, and overall inverter performance. The use of AEC-qualified components improves the long-term reliability and adaptability of the design for future automotive-grade or extended-life applications.

Unlike previous works, this design emphasizes the use of AEC-qualified discrete SiC MOSFETs in a compact form factor, ensuring both industrial reliability and cost-effective scalability for residential HVAC applications.

II. HARDWARE DESIGN

The frequency inverter is built as a classical two-level voltage source inverter (VSI), with the topology shown in Figure 1. Multilevel topologies will be considered in the future.

Fig. 1. Topology of the designed frequency inverter

The choice of the power MOSFET was dictated by several criteria. In a three-phase inverter, there are essentially two design options. A three-phase power module or design with discrete components. Regardless of the selected solution, in both cases drivers, galvanic isolation, current and temperature measurement need to be added. The advantage of the module is the smaller and compact footprint. On the other hand, a major disadvantage of the module is the higher price. For the application and design parameters described, the module solution was about twice as expensive as the discrete solution

TABLE I
SELECTED PARAMETERS OF THE USED SiC MOSFET, TYPE
IMBG120R026M2HXTMA1, MANUFACTURER INFINEON
TECHNOLOGIES

V_{DSS} [V]	1200	at $T_{vj} = 25^\circ\text{C}$
I_{DDC} [A]	53	at $T_c = 100^\circ\text{C}$
$R_{DS(on)}$ [$m\Omega$]	25.4	at $V_{gs} = 18\text{ V}$, $T_{vj} = 25^\circ\text{C}$

Fig. 2. Partial schematic of one SiC MOSFET with gate driver, inverter version 1

(USD 170 vs. USD 78). At the same time, the heat-pump frequency inverter is not significantly size-limited. Therefore, the discrete transistor approach was selected.

The design was built with a SiC MOSFET, type IMBG120R026M2HXTMA1, manufacturer Infineon Technologies, with parameters summarized in Table I.

For the design, one of the requirements was that all components in the design should be AEC (Automotive Electronics Council) automotive qualified, and if they are not, qualified components should exist in the same package. The relevant standards required are AEC-Q100, AEC-Q101 and AEC-Q200 respectively, depending on the component type. This allows future replacement of unqualified components if necessary.

For the gate driver, there were several requirements. First, the driver should be galvanically isolated. Second, the driver should include hardware fault detection so that it can turn off the transistor in case of a fault without the interaction of the external control system. Third, the driver should measure the temperature of the transistor so that the individual temperature is available for all six transistors in the frequency inverter.

In accordance with the requirements given above, the gate driver UCC21755-Q1, manufactured by Texas Instruments, was selected. The isolated DC/DC converter for the gate driver providing +15 V and -3 V is built around UCC14241-Q1 Isolated DC/DC module. The output current measurement is performed with the Reinforced Isolated Delta-Sigma Modulator with Integrated DC / DC Converter, type AMC3306M05-Q1. A partial schematic of one transistor with the driver is shown in Figure 2.

A critical aspect of inverter design is the gate driver design.

Fig. 3. Layout of the SiC MOSFET gate driver. The OUTH path is shown in orange, the OUTL path in blue, gate drive voltage in green and the return path in light blue.

It is shown in Figure 3. The distance between the gate driver and the SiC MOSFET gate has to be as short as possible, with a small inductance. This prevents overshoot. In addition, the gate resistor has to be chosen accordingly. When too small, there will be ringing on the gate voltage. When too large, the turn-on and turn-off times will be large, leading to larger switching losses. In Figure 3 the distance between the gate driver and the SiC MOSFET gate is approximately 10 mm, with a return path in a plane directly beneath the top side PCB tracks. This minimizes inductance. The used driver has a push pull output, providing independent control of turn-on and turn-off times. The OUTH path is shown in orange, the OUTL path in blue, the gate drive voltage in green, and the return path in light blue.

The design was first built as separate half-bridge modules on separate printed circuit boards (PCB). This allows for the stacking of PCBs, forming a three-phase frequency inverter. For stacking purposes, a PC / 104-Plus connector is used, although it does not respect the PC / 104 signal layout. The inverter current is fed by large pin headers on the other side of the PCB. The assembled three-phase stack is shown in Figure 4. The SiC MOSFETs are not shown in Figure 4 since they are on the bottom side of the PCB. The SiC MOSFETs are placed in the middle of the PCB.

As found experimentally, one drawback of the described solution was heat dissipation. Because the SiC MOSFETs are soldered directly to the PCB, the majority of the heat produced is directed to the PCB and not to the transistor heat sink. Therefore, another heat sink is required on the PCB. During testing, the design was found to work properly; however, the full required power was not achieved due to described thermal limitations. Therefore, it was decided to design a new circuit version.

Version 2 of the frequency inverter followed a sim-

Fig. 4. Assembled three phase stack, inverter version 1, SiC MOSFETs not visible (on PCB bottom side), left - high current headers, right - PC/104-Plus signal connector

TABLE II
SELECTED PARAMETERS OF THE USED THT SiC MOSFET, TYPE IMW120R020M1HXKSA1, MANUFACTURER INFINEON TECHNOLOGIES

V_{DSS} [V]	1200	at $T_{vj} = 25^\circ\text{C}$
I_{DDC} [A]	98	at $T_c = 25^\circ\text{C}$
$R_{DS(on)}$ [$m\Omega$]	19	at $V_{gs} = 18\text{ V}$, $T_{vj} = 25^\circ\text{C}$

ilar concept. The surface mount SiC MOSFET was replaced with a through hole (THT) SiC MOSFET IMW120R020M1HXKSA1, manufacturer Infineon Technologies, with parameters summarized in Table II. The transistor is in the TO247 package. This allows one to mount the transistor directly on the heat sink for heat spreading, without the necessity to remove heat from the PCB. The circuit was kept the same, except that the output voltage of the DC / DC converter was increased from +15 V to +18 V and from -3 V to -5 V respectively. The three-phase inverter was placed on a single PCB, with dimensions of 100x100 mm, with components on both sides of the PCB. The three-phase inverter is shown in the visualization in Figure 5. The TO247 SiC MOSFETs are from the bottom of the PCB. The PCB was made in a PCIe style, to allow stacking with other cards in the inverter, such as input/output card and control card.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The frequency inverter design was verified by connecting to an induction motor on a dynamometer. The control signals were generated with an STM32 microcontroller, with V/f control in open loop. The purpose of the testing was to test the frequency inverter, the future control system will be built on a Texas Instruments microcontroller.

The design was tested with increasing DC link voltage. First with a lab power supply, then with a 200 V dynamo, then with a 600 V variable supply.

Fig. 5. Visualization of three phase inverter, inverter version 2, SiC MOSFETs only partly visible (on PCB bottom side)

The V/f ratio was manually adjusted to keep the induction motor supplied properly. The experimental results with the inverter running at $V_{dc} = 300\text{ V}$, $I_{in} = 6\text{ A}$ supplying an induction motor loaded by 17 Nm at 676 min^{-1} (25 Hz) are shown in Figure III. In this figure, three periods of the phase current can be seen. It can be seen that the generated current is properly symmetric and sinusoidal. The large noise on Ch4 (current probe in motor phase L2) is caused by the current probe picking up the switching noise. Another probe type, from a different manufacturer, was used to probe the current in the L1 motor phase (Ch1 yellow); here the noise is significantly reduced. The maximum value of the current is approximately 8 A . The ripple in the V_{ds} voltages of both transistors is caused by the actual ripple in the voltage V_{dc} , not by the actions of the inverter. The V_{dc} voltage was supplied from a booster, with a three-phase diode rectifier with smoothing capacitors. The size of the V_{dc} ripple is about 50 V , it is varying with load and is caused by the properties of the three-phase diode rectifier with smoothing capacitors.

A detail of voltage V_{ds} for both transistors is shown in Figure 7. It shows the turn-on and turn-off events of the transistor. This is important to detect eventual voltage ringing and overshoots, endangering the transistors. From the measurement, it can be seen that there is no significant ringing that would stress the components. For example, the voltage V_{ds} of the L1 BOT transistor has no ringing. The V_{ds} voltage of the L1 TOP transistor has some small ringing visible, in the order of about 25 V . With respect to the value of $V_{ds} = 260\text{ V}$, this is about 10 percent and is completely acceptable. The amount of ringing changes slightly depending on which time instant is displayed. The currents in motor phase L1 and L2 are also shown in Figure 7. However, because of the large zoom of the current sine wave, the displayed current should be mostly constant. The visible ringing on the current in motor phase

Fig. 6. Experimental results, inverter running at $V_{dc} = 300\text{ V}$, $I_{in} = 6\text{ A}$ with induction motor loaded by 17 Nm at 676 min^{-1} (25 Hz), $P_{out} = 1.2\text{ kW}$. Ch1 (yellow) and Ch4 (blue) = motor L1 and L2 currents respectively, Ch2 (green) = V_{ds} voltage of L1 TOP transistor, Ch3 (brown) = V_{ds} voltage of L1 BOT transistor.

Fig. 7. Experimental results - details of V_{ds} , inverter running at $V_{dc} = 260\text{ V}$, $I_{in} = 8.5\text{ A}$ with induction motor loaded by 16.5 Nm at 500 min^{-1} (25 Hz), $P_{out} = 860\text{ W}$. Ch1 (yellow) and Ch4 (blue) = motor L1 and L2 currents respectively, Ch2 (green) = V_{ds} voltage of L1 TOP transistor, Ch3 (brown) = V_{ds} voltage of L1 BOT transistor. V_{ds} of the L1 BOT transistor has no ringing. V_{ds} voltage of the L1 TOP transistor has small ringing in the order of about 25 V

L2 (ch4 - blue) is caused by interference on the probe output signal. The ringing is not present in reality on the current. This was verified with another current probe and by moving the probe and its cabling to another position.

The measured results for the induction motor operating at its 83 percent nominal power are shown in Figure III. The 2.5 kW correspond to 50 percent of the inverter nominal power. A large noise on the motor phase current L2 is again visible. As explained earlier, the reason is the noisy probe, not the inverter. The voltage ripple on the V_{dc} voltage can be seen as well. Due to the larger power consumption from the used diode rectifier, this ripple is large. However, the frequency inverter and the connected motor operate normally.

The detail of V_{ds} for both transistors for the inverter running at 2.5 kW is shown in Figure 9. It can be seen that both

Fig. 8. Experimental results, inverter running 83 percent of motor power (inverter power 50 percent nominal), at $V_{dc} = 600$ V, $I_{in} = 5.2$ A with induction motor loaded by 17 Nm at 1428 min^{-1} (50 Hz), $P_{out} = 2.5$ kW. Ch1 (yellow) and Ch4 (blue) = motor L1 and L2 currents respectively, Ch2 (green) = V_{ds} voltage of L1 TOP transistor, Ch3 (brown) = V_{ds} voltage of L1 BOT transistor

Fig. 9. Experimental results, - details of V_{ds} , inverter running 83 percent of motor power (inverter power 50 percent nominal), at $V_{dc} = 600$ V, $I_{in} = 5.2$ A with induction motor loaded by 17 Nm at 1428 min^{-1} (50 Hz), $P_{out} = 2.5$ kW. Ch1 (yellow) and Ch4 (blue) = motor L1 and L2 currents respectively, Ch2 (green) = V_{ds} voltage of L1 TOP transistor, Ch3 (brown) = V_{ds} voltage of L1 BOT transistor

voltages have smooth transitions without any ringing stressing the components.

To improve clarity, the key results from Figures through are summarized in Table III. The table lists the operating conditions, output power, and observed switching behavior, including overshoot and ringing levels. This provides a concise overview of the inverter's performance, even when detailed waveform features may be difficult to discern in reduced-size figures.

The temperature of the frequency inverter heat sink was measured during the 2.5 kW motor load shown in Figure III and Figure 9. After about 15 minutes of operation at this load, the temperature reached 35 C with natural convection.

Surprisingly, the thermal issue is in the DC/DC converters supplying the gate drivers. Although the manufacturer of the

Fig. 10. Thermal measurement, SiC MOSFETs on the left, middle = DC/DC converters for gate drivers, inverter not loaded with power.

2W isolated DC/DC converters claims "high efficiency", the actual efficiency is only about 55 percent. Therefore, the DC/DC converter is the largest source of heat on the PCB. Even without inverter load, it heats up to about 67 °C. An example of this heating is shown in Figure 10 where the heat sink of SiC MOSFETs was removed. The SiC MOSFETs are on the left, inverter is not supplying current to motor, gate driver DC/DC converters are running. It can be seen that the DC/DC converters produce excessive heat. For this reason, the Ti DC/DC converters will be removed in the future PCB revision. Their low efficiency and excessive heat production are unacceptable.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The presented SiC inverter for a residential heat pump was successfully designed and experimentally validated. Two design iterations were implemented: the first using surface mount SiC MOSFETs and the second with TO-247 through-hole MOSFETs. The transition to the through-hole package significantly improved thermal management by transferring heat directly to the heatsink rather than the PCB, enabling stable inverter operation at 2.5 kW output power with natural convection. The measured heatsink temperature stabilized at only 35 °C under natural convection after 15 minutes of operation, demonstrating a favorable thermal profile compared to a typical silicon IGBT inverter of similar power, which often requires forced cooling.

A notable challenge identified in the prototype was the excessive heating of the isolated DC/DC converters for the gate drivers. Despite the manufacturer's claim of "high efficiency," the devices achieved only about 55% efficiency, leading to a

TABLE III
SUMMARY OF EXPERIMENTAL WAVEFORM MEASUREMENTS

Test Condition	DC Link Voltage	Output Power	Observed Overshoot / Ringing	Notes
Fig. 6 (25 Hz, 17 Nm)	300 V	1.2 kW	≈ 50 V DC ripple, no harmful ringing	Symmetric sinusoidal currents; probe noise visible on L2
Fig. 7 (25 Hz, 16.5 Nm)	260 V	0.86 kW	~ 25 V ringing on TOP transistor ($\approx 10\%$ of V_{ds})	BOT transistor Vds smooth; L2 probe interference
Fig. 8 (50 Hz, 17 Nm)	600 V	2.5 kW (83% motor rating)	Large DC link ripple due to rectifier	Stable inverter operation; L2 probe noise visible
Fig. 9 (detail of Fig. 8)	600 V	2.5 kW	Smooth transitions, no significant ringing	Confirms safe switching behavior
Thermal test (15 min)	600 V	2.5 kW	–	Heatsink stabilized at 35 °C under natural convection
Gate-driver DC/DC (idle)	Idle (no load)	0 kW	–	Converters self-heated to 67 °C without inverter load

measured self-heating of 67 °C even without inverter load. This thermal issue was more critical than the SiC power stage itself and will be addressed in future board revisions by replacing the DC/DC converters with higher-efficiency alternatives.

Compared with industry benchmarks, the advantages of the SiC approach become evident. Conventional silicon IGBT-based inverters for HVAC and heat pump applications typically achieve efficiencies in the range of 94 to 96%, with higher switching losses and higher cooling requirements [1], [3]. In contrast, studies report that SiC MOSFET inverters can reduce switching losses by up to 50% and conduction losses by up to 80%, allowing efficiencies greater than 97–98% under comparable conditions [1], [3], [9]. Swamy et al. [3], for example, showed that SiC-based variable frequency drives (VFDs) achieved 1 to 2 percentage points higher efficiency than silicon designs, particularly under partial load operation, a critical regime for residential heat pumps. Furthermore, SiC devices enable higher switching frequencies, allowing a reduction in passive component size without sacrificing efficiency, resulting in more compact and potentially quieter systems [3], [4].

The experimental results from this work are consistent with these trends: the inverter demonstrated stable sinusoidal output currents and low switching stress at up to 2.5 kW, with minimal voltage ringing (10% of V_{ds}). The thermal performance under natural convection confirms the reduced cooling demand expected from SiC technology. Although full efficiency measurements are ongoing, the presented data strongly suggest that the prototype will exceed the performance envelope of silicon-based inverters for similar applications.

These results demonstrate that SiC-based inverters are not only technically feasible but also a practical and industrially relevant solution for improving the energy efficiency of residential HVAC systems.

As summarized in Table III, the measured switching transitions were smooth, with only minor ringing ($\sim 10\%$ of V_{ds}) observed under certain conditions, confirming the robustness of the design.

In summary, the developed inverter highlights the practical benefits of SiC technology for residential heat pumps. The

combination of higher expected efficiency ($>97\%$), improved thermal management, and the use of AEC-qualified components establishes a clear pathway toward industrial deployment. The findings underscore not only the feasibility of SiC in low- to mid-power HVAC systems but also its potential to deliver meaningful energy savings and reliability improvements compared to conventional silicon-based solutions. Although the present validation was limited to 2.5 kW due to laboratory constraints, the design margin supports extension to the full 5 kW rating, which will be validated in ongoing work. Future work will focus on refining auxiliary circuits, implementing advanced control algorithms, and conducting full-power endurance tests to further validate the design.

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